

Theorem on the Binomial Coefficient for Positive Real Number

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Abstract: This paper presents a theorem for computing a binomial coefficient with positive real number. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real world problems.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computation, binomial coefficient, real number

1. Introduction

A geometric series with binomial coefficients [1-17] is derived from the multiple summations of a geometric series [17-27]. The binomial coefficient V_n^r is defined as a coefficient of x^k in the geometric series $\sum_{i=0}^n x^i$.

Let us see the geometric series with binomial coefficients that is derived from the multiple summations of a geometric series [28-40].

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \text{ and } V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!},$$

where r is a positive integer and n is a non-negative integer.

$$\text{Note that } V_n^0 = V_0^0 = 0! = 1 \text{ and } V_0^r = \frac{(0+1)(0+2)(0+3)\cdots(0+r)}{r!} = \frac{r!}{r!} = 1.$$

2. Binomial Coefficient for Real Number

Theorem 2.1: $V_x^{i+1} = V_x^i + (V_x^{i+1} - V_x^i)$, where i is a positive integer, x is a positive real number, and $V_0^i = 1$.

Proof:

Let us prove this theorem using the expansion of V_n^r .

$$\begin{aligned} V_x^i + (V_x^{i+1} - V_x^i) &= \\ V_x^i + \left\{ \frac{(x+1)(x+2)(x+3)\cdots(x+i)(x+i+1)}{(i+1)!} - \frac{(x+1)(x+2)(x+3)\cdots((x+i))}{i!} \right\} &= \\ = V_x^i + \left\{ \frac{(x+1)(x+2)(x+3)\cdots((x+i))}{i!} \left(\frac{(x+i+1)}{(i+1)} - 1 \right) \right\} &= V_x^i + V_{x-1}^{i+1} \\ = \frac{(x+1)(x+2)(x+3)\cdots((x+i))}{i!} + \frac{x(x+1)(x+2)(x+3)\cdots((x+i))}{(i+1)!} &= \\ \frac{(x+1)(x+2)(x+3)\cdots((x+i))}{i!} \left(1 + \frac{x}{i+1} \right) &= V_x^{i+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

Theorem 2.2: $V_x^i = V_x^{i+1} - (V_x^{i+1} - V_x^i)$, where i is a positive integer, x is a positive real number, and $V_0^i = 1$.

Proof:

Let us prove this theorem using the expansion of V_n^r .

$$\begin{aligned} V_x^{i+1} - (V_x^{i+1} - V_x^i) &= V_x^{i+1} - V_{x-1}^{i+1}, \text{ (see the Theorem 2.1)} \\ &= \left\{ \left(\frac{(x+1)(x+2)(x+3) \cdots (x+i)(x+i+1)}{(i+1)!} \right) - \left(\frac{x(x+1)(x+2)(x+3) \cdots ((x+i))}{(i+1)!} \right) \right\} \\ &= \frac{x+1)(x+2)(x+3) \cdots (x+i)}{(i+1)!} (x+i+1-x) = V_x^i. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

Let us use both variables in a binomial coefficient V_x^y as positive real numbers, i.e. x and y are positive real numbers.

$$V_x^y = V_x^{i.f} = V_x^i + (V_x^{i+1} - V_x^i) \times f.$$

For example, $y = i.f = 4.9 = 4 + 0.9$ where 4 is the integer part and 0.9 the fractional part,

$$i. e., \quad V_x^{4.9} = V_x^4 + (0.9)(V_x^4 - V_x^3).$$

(OR)

$$V_x^y = V_x^{i.f} = V_x^{i+1} - (1 - 0.f)(V_x^{i+1} - V_x^i).$$

For example, $y = i.f = 4.9 = 4 + 0.9$,

$$i. e., \quad V_x^{4.9} = V_x^5 - (0.1)(V_x^5 - V_x^3).$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, a theorem has been introduced to compute the binomial coefficients for positive real numbers. This technique can be used as an application in computing and mathematical sciences.

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